

THERMAL-ENERGETIC ANALYSIS OF A POLICY HOUSING PROTOTYPE WITH DIFFERENT ORIENTATIONS IN 3 LOCATIONS FROM ARGENTINA

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ABSTRACT

“Casa Propia” is mortgage credit line financed by the state within the public housing policy PROCREAR. This program allows houses construction based on the choice of a prototype. The objective of this work is to analyze the energy requirement of two of the eight prototypes available for this credit. The analysis is carried out in a four possible sites matrix with different orientations on three localities of Argentina. The conclusions address the multiplicity of possible scenarios regarding the energy requirement of homes due to the lack of consideration of the climatic context.

KEYWORDS

Social housing; Sustainable Architecture; Energy Efficiency.

INTRODUCTION

Based on the economic slowdown suffered by Argentina in 2011, the national government seeks a way out of the crisis through, between others policies, the Program of the Argentinian Bicentenary Credit for single family’s home (PROCREAR). The program had as objective to deliver 400 thousand house credits during the period 2012-2015. On this way, the program is consolidated as a new habitational policy cycle. As it is a program for the middle economic sector, which had lost the access to mortgage credit because of the economic situation, PROCREAR was perceived as a unique opportunity by its beneficiaries (Ventura, 2020).

PROCREAR II is a territorial, urban and housing development state federal policy with an integral perspective that seeks to improve the access to habitat conditions (Ministerio de Desarrollo Territorial y Hábitat, 2022). On its second edition, it offers various solutions for different housing demands. Between them, *Casa Propia* has as a goal the generation of 264 thousand of housing solutions all over Argentina during the period from 2021 to 2023 (Ministerio de Desarrollo Territorial y Hábitat, 2022).

The credit is available for any Argentinian person between 18 and 64 years old or for foreigners with residence and formal income between one and eight minimum wages. The condition is not to be owner or co-owner from real estate except land. As another restriction, it is enhanced that it is not admit to construct in private or closed neighborhoods. Finally, the main condition, in which is based the present paper, is the restriction to construct only one of the eight house prototypes from the program. The house is chosen, between the eight prototypes, by the credit beneficiary without any restriction (Ministerio de Desarrollo Territoria y Hábitat, 2022).

The program prototypes are developed based on models which applies all over Argentina no matter the clime, or any other local condition. This homogenized and spiffed model allows to reduce the design and construction costs, at the expense of the environmental comfort and impact. Therefore, it is worth noting that it is possible to reduce the energy demand by modifying the prototypes envelope, which means an additional invest. However, it is possible to avoid cost overruns if given priority to the passive criteria from the very beginning of the design to the materialization of the building (Vanoli, Crespo Sanchez y Barroso, 2021).

Objectives

This work has three objectives. On the first place, to demonstrate, through the comparative analysis of two PROCREAR prototypes, the differences in the energy requirement and energy efficiency class of each house located on lands with different orientations in an identical locality. Second, to exhibit the energy requirements wide differences when locating the same house in three different bioclimatic zones in Argentina, as well as the differences in behavior of the two prototypes in each location. Finally, to identify the key aspects to be modified in the PROCREAR public policy, from a thermal-energy point of view.

METHODOLOGY

The methodology used in this paper is quantitative and is structured in two stages. On the first one, an analysis from the thermal requirement from two houses prototypes (Juana and Bicentenario) on four possible orientation lands and three locations (24 results) is made. On the second stage, two results comparative analysis are made. The first of them compares the results from both houses in the four orientations on each location. The second analysis compares the results from the same orientation between different locations.

First stage

The results are obtained by the on-line application (Etiquetado de Viviendas, 2021) which is promoted by the Nation Energy Secretary, according to IRAM 1900 standard (2017). From this, the characteristic IPE value (Energy Performance Index) is obtained, which is expressed in kWh/m²year. The Energy efficiency class (From A to G) and the annual secondary energy consumption (kWh/year) are also obtained from the on-line application.

IPE is a house characteristic value that represents the primary energy requirement over a normal use, during a year, by surface unit (m²) to satisfied the requirements from heating, cooling, illumination and hot water production. Said value defines the Energy Efficiency Class (scale from A to G) that determines the Energy Efficiency label. The values range from IPE are specific for the different regions of the country.

The locations selected are based on the pilot test carried on six cities from Argentina which have different value ranges to determine IPE and energy label (Subsecretaria de Energías Renovables y Eficiencia Energética, 2019). From the available cities with data, the local authors city is selected (SMT); CABA as a warm temper climate exponent and, finally, SCB as cold weather exponent. For SMT the energy label encompass a range from 20 kWh/m²year (class A) to 200 kWh/m²year (class F); for CABA the label goes from 30 kWh/m²year (class A) to 270 kWh/m²year (class F); and for SCB, the label span from 110 kWh/m²year (class A) to 1065 kWh/m²year (class F). In all the cases, any value bigger than the class F is considered class G.

From the technical information provided by the Argentinians Habitat and Territorial Development Ministry (Ministerio de Desarrollo Territorio y Hábitat, 2022) and from the on-line calculator, the energy requirement from the houses Juana and Bicentenario is carried out, in four possible hypothetical land orientations: north, east, south and west.

Second stage

From the results obtained, two comparative analyses are made:

The comparative analysis of a group of terrains with the four possible orientations on the same location. Its objective is to determine which is the most effective orientation and which prototype has less energy requirements on each orientation.

The results comparative analysis on the same terrain orientation on the three locations, has two objectives: on one hand to determine which is the most efficient prototype on each location for the same orientation and, on the other hand, to know, according to the energy efficiency class, in which location is more efficient for one prototype for the same orientation.

Study cases

Two prototypes are aleatory selected:

The first one, *Juana*. The dwelling is projected to be located between partition walls in a 10.00 m wide ground and it is developed in 63.7 m². The house has a vehicular and pedestrian access; a dining living kitchen; a bathroom, two bedrooms and a bare space for a future gallery (Figure 1). The project foresees a hollow ceramic brick doble wall with air chamber; the roof is made of metallic sheet, wooden ceiling and a *tyvek* membrane as thermal and hydrophobic insulation.

Figure 1: Prototype *Juana* plan and facade.

The second selected prototype is *Bicentenario*. It is also projected to be between partition walls, in a 10.00 m wide ground and it covers an area of 52.0 m² covered and a 19.00 m² gallery. The house has a pedestrian a vehicular access; a dinning-living-kitchen, a bathroom and two bedrooms (Figure 2). The project foresees a doble wall with solid ceramic brick and hollow ceramic brick with an air chamber between them; the roof, as in *Juana* prototype, is made of metallic sheet, wooden ceiling and a *tyvek* membrane as thermal and hydrophobic insulation.

Figure 2: Prototype *Bicentenario* plan and facade.

Bioclimatics zones

Argentina is classified, according to IRAM standard in six bioclimatic zones (from I very hot to VI very cold), with two sub-zones each one (a high thermal amplitude and b low thermal amplitude). The bioclimatic zones considered in this paper, have great differences.

SMT is located in the bioclimatic zone IIb *warm*, summer is the critical season in this zone, with average medium temperatures over 24 °C and average maximum over 30 °C. The thermal amplitude is lower than 14 °C. For these reasons, there are general recommendations among which stand out: the use of light colors in exterior surfaces; big thermal insulation on roof, east and weas walls; design with mean axe east-west; protect surfaces from sun shine; avoid putting windows on east and west faces and, finally, promote cross ventilation with the design (IRAM, 2011).

CABA belongs to bioclimatic zone IIIb warm temper, it presents a relatively hot summer, with medium temperatures between 20 °C and 26 °C. Winter is not so cold, with average temperatures between 8 °C and 12 °C reaching, on few occasions, values lower than 0 °C. We can affirm that winters are relatively benign and summer not very hot. As in zone IIIb, this zone presents thermal amplitude lower than 14 °C. Regarding on design recommendations for these building, the following stand out: protecting the building west facades from sunshine; using sun protection on windows; painting with light colors the buildings envelope (IRAM, 2011).

By last, SCB is located in the bioclimatic zone VI *very cold*. The summer average temperatures are lower than 12 °C, while in winter, they reach 4 °C. Because of these values, the recommendation for buildings are: thermal insulation in walls, roof and floor; reducing windows size in all the orientations except from the north; to evaluate the condensation risks; avoiding thermal bridges (IRAM, 2011).

Figure 3: Bioenvironmental zones of Argentina. Green: SMT, light blue: CABA and red SCB.

RESULTS

The data charged on the on-line application to obtained the IPE, corresponds to the technical characteristics of each prototype provided by the PROCLEAR program. Exact measurements are taken for both cases on a terrain with 10 m front. In terms of materiality, the constructive systems present on planimetry and materials computation are loaded.

On the *Juana* house, two thermal zones are identified, according to the roof's materialization and morphology. The sector located to the front, is taken as thermal zone 1, formed by two bedrooms and

the bathroom. The bottom located sector, constituted by the dining-kitchen-living room, is taken as thermal zone 2.

In the *Bicentenario* prototype case, three thermal zone are defined, also according to the roof's morphology and materialization. The thermal zone 1 is composed by the bedroom located to the front of the terrain. The bathroom constitutes the thermal zone 2, as it has a different morphology, height and materialization roof. The thermal zone 3 are the dining-kitchen-living room and the bedroom located to the back of the house.

The obtained results show a wide values variety for both prototypes, for the different locations and orientations. It is highlighted that in no case the energy efficiency label is positioned on an efficient class (A, B or C). In the Figure 4, the 24 obtained IPE can be viewed, for the two prototypes, on three locations and for the four orientations. At first glance, it stands out the substantial difference between the IPE values for the three locations, being the ones from SCB the highest. However, the energy efficiency class accompanies these high values, so, although the energy requirement values in kWh/m2year vary, the energetic classifications (from A to G) does not have great differences for different locations.

Figure 4 : IPE and energy efficiency class for both analyzed prototypes en three locations and on four possible orientations.

The house *Juana* shows less variations on the energy benefits on the different orientations than the *Bicentenario* house. This is due to the morphological characteristics from both prototypes. The Juana prototype has windows on four orientations while the Bicentenario has only in two, front and back (Figure 5).

Figure 5. Windows orientations for the prototypes Bicentenario (to the left) and Juana (to the right).

From this point of view, the *Bicentenario* house has a little adaptability and improvement of its thermal properties by being located on a terrain with south orientation. While on the *Juana* house this possibility is discernible.

For the *Bicentenario* house case, the east orientations is the most unfavorable for the three locations (SMT, CABA y SCB). This is due to the biggest windows are oriented to the west protected by a gallery that allows the solar radiation input on summer and restricts it during the winter. The cases located to south and north are the most efficient for SMT and CABA. In SCB the most efficient orientation is the south one, being the north facade the most exposed to the solar radiation input during the winter. For this last case, the best energy efficiency class between all the variants is reached: Class E.

Another interesting variant to analyze is the secondary energy requirement for the thermal conditioning. This variant is presented as energy requirement for heating and cooling. These values are absolute and they are expressed in kWh/year, they refer to the theoretical energy consumption during a year for the entire house. Unlike the IPE, it cannot be compared between different houses typologies values because it varies with different surface and volume.

For the *Bicentenario* house, in general, is evident a bigger energy consumption for heating. On the particular case of SMT, the energy consumption for heating is similar for all the orientations, while there are important variations on the energy need to refrigerate. The north orientation has the less energetic requirement for cooling 783 kWh/year followed by the south orientation with a slightly higher level, 940 kWh/year. This happens because of the lack of windows on the east and west orientations. For the east and west orientations, the energy requirement for refrigeration is higher, 1517 kWh/year and 1447 kWh/year respectively. The CABA situation is similar than the SMT one, but with slightly higher values, being also the north and south orientations the ones with less energy requirement for cooling. The SCB case presents a particular situation, very important energetic requirement for heating and minimum requirement for refrigeration, this is because of the climatic characteristics of the bioclimatic zone VI very cold.

Table1. Secondary energy requirement for thermal conditioning in *Bicentenario* model.

ORIENTATION	LOCATION	SECONDARY ENERGY REQUIREMENT (kWh/year)	
		HEATING	COOLING
NORTH	SMT	1271	783
	CABA	1995	697
	SCB	10893	134
SOUTH	SMT	1165	940
	CABA	1843	921
	SCB	8633	173
EAST	SMT	1551	1517
	CABA	2574	1368
	SCB	15003	266
WEST	SMT	1223	1447
	CABA	1934	1298
	SCB	8519	254

Figure 6. Secondary energy requirement for thermal conditioning in *Bicentenaria* model.

In the Juana house, is also evident a bigger energy requirement for heating than for cooling. On this case, the main variations are between locations (SMT, CABA and SCB) and the differences between the different orientations (north, south, east and west) are not very significant. It can be seen on figure 7, that the energy requirement values for heating and refrigerating remain practically constant on each location.

Tabla 2. Secondary energy requirement for thermal conditioning in *Juana* model.

ORIENTATION	LOCATION	SECONDARY ENERGY REQUIREMENT (kWh/year)	
		HEATING	COOLING
NORTH	SMT	1764	814
	CABA	2367	709
	SCB	13246	132
SOUTH	SMT	1426	833
	CABA	2282	749
	SCB	12749	143
EAST	SMT	1359	931
	CABA	2236	844
	SCB	12633	165
WEST	SMT	1500	866
	CABA	2440	750
	SCB	13427	140

Figure 6. Secondary energy requirement for thermal conditioning in *Juana* model.

CONCLUSIONS

These papers results allow to account for two types of behaviors on both PROCREAR prototypes. On the four orientations analysis, which remains constant in the three locations studied, the prototype *Juana*

has slight variations on its IPE and remains constant the energy efficiency class (class F). This behavior replies in the three locations by variate the orientation from the maximum to the minimum IPE, being north and south the smaller IPEs values for SMT and CABA, meanwhile in SCB the smaller are east and south. On the other hand, the *Bicentenario* prototype has considerable variations on its IPE as on its energy efficiency class for each orientation. Said behavior remains in the three locations and the values intensifies in SCB. The variations reach the minimum IPE on the north and south orientations, with a energy efficiency class mobility from F to G, in SMT and CABA, meanwhile in SCB the minimum levels are registered in south and east orientations, with a label class mobility that reaches E, F and G.

Likewise, it highlights the significant increase in the absolute IPE values and the secondary energy requirement by situating the prototypes on locations with different bioclimatic zones. Even though the energy efficiency class values are almost constant, the lack of an envelope with better benefits for the cold weather increased the absolute values. In this way, the analysis of two prototypes allows us to identify two types of behaviors and multiple results around the IPE, Energy Efficiency Class and Secondary Energy Requirement. The question is whether the rest of the 6 existing prototypes will present other types of behaviors or will be added to those identified in this study.

PROCREAR is an exceptional housing policy for Argentina, which represents an unprecedented opportunity for its beneficiaries. However, from the analysis carried out, we can infer that the prototypes design does not have bioclimatic considerations that incorporates the climatic context as a study variable. This lack is added to the shortage of information about the model's energetic behavior on a program where every beneficiary can choose freely the prototype, which cancels the possibility of chosen the house with a thermal-energetic criteria.

In agreement with Segura and Cosacov (2019), the knowledge accumulated from the analysis of various experiences with PROCREAR prototypes, allow to identify potentialities, limitations and omissions in this housing policy, that should feedback the future public policies generation, design and implementation. This paper is entirely made with a analysis tool from the Argentinian state: software *Aplicativo de Cálculo (Etiquetado de Viviendas, 2021)*, developed in a public policy of energy efficiency context, to make manifest the lack of entailment between this tool and the PROCREAR, and, through the reached results, to show the richness of a possible entailment.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare that they have no conflicts of interest associated with the work presented in this paper.

DATA AVAILABILITY

Data on which this paper is based is available from the authors upon reasonable request.